

Scope of Right to Information Act in Enabling Local Development in Nepal

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Abstract:

This paper aims to explore the impact and potential of the Right to Information (RTI) Act in advancing local development initiatives in Nepal. Historically, local development governance faced challenges, including limited awareness among stakeholders, delays in service delivery, and issues related to corruption, transparency, and accountability. Enacted in 2007, the RTI Act represents a groundbreaking legislative step, obligating public authorities to actively disclose and disseminate information to support local

development efforts. This law empowers citizens to engage more effectively with local authorities, fostering responsive and community-oriented development. The study employs qualitative methods with an exploratory and descriptive approach, using purposively selected case studies from Kathmandu Metropolitan City and Sunkoshi Rural Municipality in Okhaldhunga. The findings highlight that transparency and accountability within local government administration are essential for participatory democracy. Overall, the RTI Act is shown to be a transformative tool for citizens, significantly enhancing governance by supporting transparency, accountability, citizen involvement, and effective local development governance.

Keywords: *Governance of local development, Local authorities, Local development, Public service delivery, Right to information.*

Introduction

The United Nations, in its very first General Assembly in 1946¹, adopted a resolution (59.1) stating that freedom of information, hereafter as FOI, is a fundamental human rights and the touchstone of all the freedoms on which the United Nations is consecrated. Florine (2007) argues that the line is not quite right: information by itself is not power. But information is vital to the exercise of economic and political power. Opening up channels of information brings about changes in who can do what. However,

over the past few decades, we have witnessed increased awareness among citizens from all parts of the world, demanding more information and an end to secretive decision-making. As a result, laws regarding public access to information about government services have been adopted by the United Kingdom, Japan, India, South Africa, Mexico, and a host of other countries.

RTI Initiatives in Nepal

In Nepal, the Right to Information (RTI) has only recently gained recognition as a

¹ UN General Assembly Resolution 1946

fundamental citizen's right, on par with other constitutional rights. Although the right to access information was acknowledged in the 1990 Constitution, it was not actively implemented until the RTI Act was enacted in July 2007. The Act, passed by Nepal's Parliament, aimed to fulfill the fundamental rights of citizens to seek, receive, and disseminate information on matters of public significance managed by public agencies (Dahal, 2010). Nepal was the third country in South Asia to adopt an RTI law, following Pakistan (2002) and India (2005). However, Nepal was the first in the region to constitutionally recognize the right to information, as Article 16 of the 1990 Constitution explicitly guaranteed it. This commitment continued in the Interim Constitution (Article 27) and remains upheld in Article 27 of the Constitution of Nepal 2015.

The Nepalese Legislature-Parliament endorsed the RTI Act, acknowledging several points. The Act's Preamble says that the law was adopted because a legal arrangement for RTI is desirable "so that the state functioning or mechanism is made open and transparent government with the democratic institution to make it accountable and responsible towards the citizen; to ease the general public's access to information of public interest; to protect sensitive information that could be damaging to the interests of the nation as well as citizens; and to protect and implement the citizen's right to information."² RTI movements underscore the principle of maximum disclosure, asserting that all information held by public bodies should generally be accessible to the public, with restrictions applied only in rare, justified cases. The RTI Act was designed to establish a practical framework for citizens' right to information, acknowledging that access to information is a fundamental right. In democratic societies, individuals have the right to freedom of opinion and expression, which includes the ability to hold public opinions and to seek, receive, and share information from public authorities. Accessible and accurate information empowers citizens to lead dignified lives within a responsible society (Dahal, 2010).

² Right To Information Act, 2007

The RTI Act of 2007 resulted from sustained efforts by the media and civil society organizations, marking significant progress in ensuring freedom of information in Nepal. These efforts also led to the establishment of the National Information Commission (NIC) on June 14, 2008, an independent body dedicated to promoting and safeguarding the right to information, along with the approval of the RTI Regulation on February 9, 2009. The contributions of Nepalese civil society and media have been instrumental in institutionalizing freedom of information and fostering a transparent and equitable information regime. This commitment to promoting, protecting, and practicing information access serves as the foundation of a transparent, democratic society in Nepal

RTI provides citizens with the opportunity to be informed of what the government does for them, why, and how it does it. The Act enables every citizen to access public information from government records, like budget allocation, expenses of development and administrative activities, government decisions, public service delivery policies and procedures, and all kinds of income or expenditure of the government. To intensify the process of paradigm shift from the state-centric to the citizen-centric model of local development, the RTI Moment in Nepal came into existence, which prevents access to information and recognizes seeking information as a fundamental right to promote transparent, accountable, responsible, participatory, and decentralized development administration.

Local Development and RTI

Local development governance encompasses the combined efforts of various entities to improve quality of life, enhance public satisfaction, promote economic growth, and conserve the environment at the local level. A community plays a central role in local development, driven by its own interests and active participation in realizing these goals. Assessing the effectiveness of local development governance is essential to strengthening local authorities' impact on socio-economic

advancements. Key measures—such as reforming public service delivery, fostering transparency, and promoting accountability—are instrumental in making local governance more people-centered. The Right to Information (RTI) Act serves as a vital tool in enabling transparent governance in local communities, reducing information disparities, and curbing corruption. Since its enactment, the RTI Act has contributed to increased responsiveness and accountability in public service and development administration.

RTI holds transformative potential, empowering citizens, civil society, media, activist groups, and NGOs to engage meaningfully in the local development process, fostering a more inclusive and participatory approach. By simply enacting the RTI Act, ordinary citizens have gained a powerful mechanism to question public decisions, scrutinize expenditures, and verify beneficiary lists and selection criteria. This empowerment is particularly significant for local development, governance, administration, monitoring, participation, advocacy, and democracy. In an era where information is increasingly viewed as fundamental to human rights, access to information has become as essential as basic needs like food and shelter. Consequently, RTI represents a substantial contribution to strengthening local development and governance.

Objective of the Study

The general objective of the study is to assess and review the scope of the RTI Act in enabling the governance of local development in Nepal. The specific objectives of this study are to:

- Explore the issues of local development in the perspective of governance and administrative system, and
- Assess the scope of the RTI Act to resolve the issues of governance of local development in Nepal

Methodology

This research is qualitative and based on descriptive analysis, relying primarily on

exploration and description. Structured interview and observations of the public service delivery system of the local government, the quality of development activities, people's participation in the development activities, and the relationship of stakeholders between the information demand side and the information supply side were conducted. It is based on both secondary and primary data.

For the study, Kathmandu metropolitan city in Kathmandu and Sunkoshi rural municipality in Okhaldhunga were selected purposively. The selection of the local governments is based on the representation of municipalities and rural municipalities. The selected palikas can't cover the entire local government of the county, but they can represent all regions and all types of palikas. As a sample size, there were three beneficiaries from the demand or information seekers side and three public authorities from the supply or information keeper side from each palika, respectively. Among them, a journalist, a RTI activist, and a general citizen were selected as information seekers, and the mayor/chairperson, chief executive officer, and information officer were selected as information keepers from each palika, respectively.

Analysis and Results

Issues of Local Development in Nepal

Local development governance relies on a variety of factors, including administrative capacity, the nation's level of development, external influences, and the availability of technology and information to support decision-making. The World Bank highlights challenges in development governance relevant to both developed and developing nations. Key elements involve political and administrative dimensions, such as political accountability, citizen acceptance of the political system, and regular elections to legitimize political authority. Freedom of association and active participation by diverse groups—religious, social, economic, cultural, and professional—are essential for inclusive governance. An established legal framework rooted in the rule of law, alongside

judicial independence, is crucial to uphold human rights, ensure social justice, and protect against misuse of power. Accessible information is also essential for shaping public policies, making informed decisions, and monitoring governance effectiveness. Effective administration must prioritize efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and cooperation between government entities and civil society organizations.

Challenges hindering local development governance include corruption, power centralization, politicization, human rights abuses, weak legislative capacity, limited citizen participation, underactive civil society, disempowered grassroots democratic institutions, and poor coordination among political and community-level organizations. Additionally, judicial delays and limited involvement of disadvantaged groups in decision-making processes impede local governance progress.

This study assesses how the Right to Information (RTI) Act can address these challenges and improve local development governance. It provides an analytical foundation to explore how RTI can resolve issues affecting governance at the local level. Citizens currently face obstacles in public service delivery, such as delays, lack of transparency, and corruption. Enacted in 2007, the RTI Act is critical

legislation that grants citizens access to information from public authorities, aiming to enhance decision-making transparency in local governance. By reducing unnecessary secrecy, the Act enables individuals and groups to stay informed about decisions that impact them. This increased transparency fosters participatory democracy by involving citizens in administrative and political processes. The RTI Act is seen as a powerful tool for improving local governance in Nepal, supporting democratic participation, accountability, transparency, and citizen empowerment, and fostering a balance of power between rights holders and duty bearers for better governance outcomes

Scope of RTI in Local Development

The RTI Act is an important legislative measure aimed at keeping citizens informed about the activities of the government and maintaining good governance in development administration. So, the study has assessed the role of RTI in enabling local development governance in Nepal. The assessment was done with Kathmandu Metropolitan City and Sunkoshi Rural Municipality where more than 30 local development issues forwarded for consideration by the RTI phenomenon. Those are demand-side indicators for the public to fulfill from the supply side or local government authority.

Table 1. Responses on Specific Issues and that can be solved with RTI

SN	Issues of local development	Responses in Percentage (%)		
		Kathmandu	Sunkoshi	Average
1	Communication gap	100	100	100
2	Delays in service delivery	84	100	92
3	Wastage of time	84	100	92
4	Wrong Users committee selection	100	100	100
5	Un-transparent system of local government	84	100	92
6	Benefits to Non-Poor	84	100	92
7	Dependency on Government	100	100	100
8	Poor participation of beneficiaries	84	100	92
9	Agencies involved for the misuse of fund	84	100	92
10	Poor control of government agencies with poor beneficiaries	84	100	92
11	Lack of coordination	84	100	92
12	Paperwork based Implementation Complexities	84	84	84
13	Over lapping	84	84	84
14	Lack of awareness	84	100	92

15	Leakages	84	100	92
16	Lack of accountability	84	100	92
17	Absence of people's participation	84	84	84
18	Centralized trend of planning and deciding local priorities	100	100	100
19	High Cost of delivery	84	100	92
20	Absence of actual monitoring	100	84	92
21	Absence of actual evaluation	84	100	92
22	Lot of paper work	84	84	84
23	Use of less materials in construction than shown in the estimates or in the bills and vouchers	100	84	92
24	Payment to fictitious workers listed in muster rolls	84	100	92
25	Government programs in contravention of established rules	100	100	100
26	Exploitation	84	84	84
27	Failure to implement social legislation such as those related to minimum wages, gender and protection of disadvantaged groups	84	100	92
28	Rights and dignity of the individual	84	100	92
29	Taking decisions that critically and adversely affect people without consulting	100	84	92
30	Failure to perform duties effectively	100	100	100
Average in all Issues		88.8 %	95.73%	97.33 %

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The above-mentioned response was taken in the form of multiple-choice questions, wherein the responses were received on identified issues. From the above data, it can be clearly understood that almost all the stakeholders believe that RTI has huge potential to solve the hurdles of local development governance. Beyond this, it has been made to get the expressive opinions of the stakeholders on what the problems are related to local development governance. Thus, from the above responses, it is being learned that people believe that RTI can be very useful in addressing the problems of local development. People responded in the form of kind and type of issues in the local development. Even people responded very specifically regarding how a particular issue can be resolved through using RTI. Beyond this, the respondent showed their concern and worry about the problems and the hope they were looking for in the instrument of RTI. The above-mentioned responses dealt with the problems that can be solved by RTI. The implementation of the RTI Act has been weak and relatively inadequate. One of the main reasons is the inadequate awareness and well-trained in public agencies. Nevertheless, there is a growing demand from civil society groups for the proper

implementation of the Act, and one study showed that awareness of the RTI legislation in Nepal. The implementation of provisions on proactive disclosure has also been weak, and none of the surveyed public authorities published all the required information on their respective websites. A large proportion of public bodies have failed to appoint information officers as required under the law. Only a small number of government bodies have designated an information officer.

Role of RTI in Enabling Local Development

Respondents considered RTI as important instrument with the help of which the governance of local development improved a lot because it can combat corruption, spread awareness amongst the masses, bring about the transparency and accountability. Likewise, RTI helps to strengthening the democracy and removing regional disparities. According to respondents, RTI can improve administrative systems as well as public service delivery. It plays a role as check on elected representatives and public authorities. Quality of service delivery and openness of local development governance can be maintained by the use of RTI act as well. Thus, the overall perception of stakeholders

about its role in reforming the governance in general and local development in particular is quite positive and ambitious.

Table 2. Perception of Respondents about RTI and Local Development

Statement About RTI	Agree with Statement in Percentage (%)	Do not Agree with Statement in Percentage (%)
The use of RTI act is very objective and productive in the development activity	87	13
The instrument of RTI act has provided as excellent opportunity to the beneficiaries for the direct and decisive participation in local development governance	83	17
RTI Act has played a vital role in containing corruption in the local development at all the stages and helped promotion of transparency in the process local development	71	29
RTI controls the irresponsible activities of people representatives and local government administrators towards local development governance.	70	30

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table No 2 makes it clear that most of the respondents believe that the use of RTI is very objective and productive in the development activity. Very little number of respondents doesn't agree with this. In case of another statement that is "The instrument of RTI act has provided an excellent opportunity to the beneficiaries for the direct and decisive participation in local development" majority of the respondents get agree with this while 13 %

don't agree with this. The same is the case with the stakeholders' perception regarding to "RTI's role combatting corruption" 71 % of the respondents believes that RTI played a role in combating corruption. 70 % respondents are agreeing that the RTI act controls the irresponsible activities of people representatives and local government administrators towards local development governance.

Table 3. Usefulness of RTI Act

Do you think that the RTI Act 2007 could be useful in strengthening the local development governance?	Numbers and Weightage of Responses in "YES"	Numbers and Weightage of Responses in "NO"
Supply Side (Mayors/Chairperson, Chief Administrative Officers and Information Officers)	5 (83.33 %)	1 (16.66%)
Demand Side (Beneficiaries, Journalists, RTI Activists/Civil Societies)	4 (66.66%)	2 (33.33 %)
RTI Experts (Experts, NIC commissioners, NIC Chief commissioner)	6 (100 %)	0
Total	15 (83.33 %)	3 (16.66 %)

Source: Field Survey, 2022

As far as the perception about usefulness of the RTI Act is concerned 83.33 % of the respondents replied affirmatively, means they believe that RTI act is useful in strengthening

local development governance. Only 16.66 % of total respondents gave negative response to this questions which is negligible one. If we analyze at the responses category wise then also the

responses seems affirmative. So, we can say that the general perception about RTI especially regarding its potentials in strengthening the local development governance is quite effective. There is no doubt that all the people believe that RTI is useful for sustainable development of local communities. Hence, the act can be considered as one of the important integral part of the effective regime of transparent, participatory and accountable local development governance.

The review and analysis of perceptions reveal that people see the Right to Information (RTI) as a vital tool for addressing issues in local development governance. Public sentiment toward the RTI Act is largely positive, with many respondents recognizing its value in resolving governance-related challenges. There is a widespread belief that, without such an Act, ordinary citizens would struggle to access necessary information, making RTI an essential legal pathway for information access. The RTI Act has the potential to intervene in a range of local development issues, providing an effective mechanism for tackling governance challenges. While the Act promotes public awareness, civil society organizations play a significant role in educating the public and could further enhance these efforts. The RTI Act also functions as an instrument of public awareness by disseminating information on government programs to people at the local level, contributing significantly to governance in local development.

However, the study indicates that the implementation of RTI has not met the Act's intended standards. While urban areas like Kathmandu show better compliance, rural areas, such as Sunkoshi, lag significantly behind. A large portion of the population, including public officials, remains unaware of the RTI Act's role in promoting effective local development governance. Many citizens lack insight into how public funds are allocated and spent, highlighting the need for greater awareness and engagement with RTI to strengthen local governance.

Findings

The RTI Act of 2007 has proven to be an effective tool for enhancing governance in local development by promoting transparency and curbing corruption. By enabling citizens to access information held by public authorities, particularly local governments, the RTI Act fosters accountability and responsible governance. Through this transparency, citizens gain insight into various development projects, budgets, and policies, which strengthens the accountability of local authorities. The Act offers a mechanism for reducing corruption and administrative inefficiencies in local governance by empowering citizens to request information and monitor officials' actions. With strategic policy adjustments and increased public awareness, the RTI's potential could be further optimized. Key findings of this study include:

- a. RTI plays a transformative role across various aspects of life—political, social, economic, cultural, and ethical—enhancing people's beliefs and ethical values.
- b. The Act promotes citizen participation in local development, enabling them to inquire about projects and decisions, thereby fostering active involvement in decision-making.
- c. Citizens can utilize RTI to access details about local development activities, budgets, and expenditures, facilitating independent oversight and evaluation of these initiatives to ensure effective implementation.
- d. RTI strengthens service delivery quality, as local development governance is grounded in transparent, open information.
- e. The Act promotes accuracy, accountability, impartiality, and public engagement in government activities.
- f. The RTI Act is a valuable tool for advancing local development governance, supporting structured and productive use in governance activities.
- g. The National Information Commission should launch extensive awareness campaigns to educate citizens on RTI, thereby encouraging their active use of this right.

h. Local authorities have not sufficiently addressed the needs of underprivileged groups regarding RTI rights, indicating a gap in inclusive governance.

i. Civil society organizations have been instrumental in RTI advocacy by collaborating with the government, civil society, and media to raise public awareness about RTI and access processes.

Conclusion

This study aimed to assess the impact of the Right to Information (RTI) Act on local development governance in Nepal, particularly in overcoming challenges like administrative delays, corruption, and lack of transparency. Findings indicate that the RTI Act enhances transparency by ensuring public access to government rules, decisions, and processes, thereby strengthening the accountability of public authorities. For effective governance, the government must not only represent but actively respond to citizens' needs. Key elements of good governance: rule of law, judicial independence, citizen participation, and social equity are integral to this framework.

To further promote effective local governance, ongoing RTI awareness campaigns should be prioritized as a joint effort by civil society, private organizations, and government. Additionally, supporting RTI activists through capacity building and resources will help sustain the Act's impact on fostering transparency, accountability, and citizen satisfaction in local development initiatives

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